

RFID BASED APPLIANCES

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Abstract: Viruses are capable of surviving on surfaces outside of the human body. It is highly likely to get exposed to SARS-CoV-2, the virus responsible for the current outbreak, by touching an infected surface or object and then touching your skin. It is wise to limit contact with alien surfaces. The proposed paper presents a solution for the touchless operation of everyday appliances like light bulbs, fans, air conditioners, etc. Touchless appliances are implemented using RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) technology. The light bulb is connected to the AC power supply and the relay module. The relay module is then connected to the Arduino UNO, which is based on the ATmega328P. The Arduino UNO is also connected to the RFID Reader component. The final circuit is capable of controlling appliances that use an AC power supply of 220V using RFID TAG and RFID reader, thus making the entire operation of switching the appliance ON and OFF completely touchless.

Index Terms - RFID, Arduino, touchless, appliances.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 Virus (SARS-CoV-2) remains a major threat to the health of the global population [1]. Pandemics have a tremendous social and economic influence on our lives. There have been several devastating pandemics in the last century [8]. Even though COVID-19 is the most recent pandemic of its kind, considering past pandemics and how technology aided people at the time can be a tremendous assistance in the current predicament. RFID technology utilizes radio waves to send data from an electronic tag called an RFID tag placed on an object through a reader for the purposes of identifying and tracking the thing. RFID is already utilized in disaster situations to monitor and identify victims. RFID permits the capture of data in real-time, quick access for emergency responders, and time savings. Using a computer database, crisis management teams, hospitals, and emergency personnel may obtain data [9]. In order to identify friendly aircraft, RFID was examined for the first time in the 1940s. Several industries, including the supply chain, agriculture, transportation, healthcare, and services, have successfully utilized RFID technology today. Examining the technologies and associated processes that contribute to disease diagnosis, illness containment, and disease prevention are vital [8]. As the first line of defense, the government can deploy a number of cutting-edge technologies. IoT is a promising technology composed of networked computer devices that automatically communicate data across the network. RFID is a component of the Internet of Things that will enable us to remotely operate multiple appliances and prevent the spread of infectious illnesses. At the time of writing, December 2022, the global count of confirmed Coronavirus cases is 658 million. Many of these cases have been caused due to the indirect spread of the virus. The fear among people to come in contact with outside surfaces is natural. Thus, limiting contact with foreign surfaces is essential. Radiofrequency identification is a technology that uses radio waves to transmit signals and then receive a response. It is generally used for the identification of objects over a distance [2]. Hence, using RFID to control appliances and avoid direct contact with foreign objects. This can lead to limiting the spread of such viruses and ensure the good health of people.

II. RFID (RADIO FREQUENCY IDENTIFICATION)

RFID (Radio frequency identification) is a data-collecting method that stores information on electronic/digital tags. There are electronic readers used to recognize the tags. An electronic tag is attached to the product. This approach is widely employed in many institutions nowadays, and it combines strong security with excellent working efficiency [5].

Fig 1: RFID System

2.1) RFID Reader

RFID system components include an RFID reader. The reader, also known as an interrogator or scanner, uses antennas to send and receive radio frequency (RF) data both from and to the tag. Multiple antennas on a reader may be responsible for sending and receiving radio waves. The reader tells the data processing system of the tagged item's existence. The control section, high-frequency interface, and antenna are its three primary components. A lot of things affect the reader's reading range. The gain, frequency, and orientation of the antenna all influence the read range. There are four distinct types of readers: fixed, mobile, read/write, and read-only. The first two are preoccupied with design and technology, whereas the latter two are preoccupied with specific items [2].

Fig 2: RFID Reader

2.2) RFID tag

RFID tags are an electronic identifying aid. Typically, it consists of two major components: an antenna, which is responsible for receiving waves, and an electrical circuit, which stores the information [4]. The RFID tags are of three different types: active tag, passive tag, and semi-passive tag. Active tags are the tags that have an inbuilt power supply. Passive tags require an external source of power that comes from the RFID reader.

Fig 3: RFID tag

The frequency of the RFID tags affects their range. The resistance to interference and other performance characteristics are determined by this frequency [3]. The use or choice of an RFID tag depends on the application; various RFID tags operate at various frequencies [6].

Table 1: Frequency Bands.

S.N.	Band	Frequency Speed	Read Rang Length/Characteristics	Application
1	Low-Frequency	100-500 KHz	Short to medium read range Inexpensive Low reading speed	Access control Animal identification Inventory control Car immobilizer
2	Intermediate	10-15 MHz	Short to medium read range Potentially inexpensive Medium reading speed	Access control Smart cards
3	High-Frequency	850-950 MHz 2.4-5.8G Hz	Long read range High reading speed Line of sight required Expensive	Railroad car monitoring Toll collection system Big and medium libraries

III. ARDUINO UNO

Programming the open-source Arduino microcontroller is simple and it is constantly updated. The first Arduino was released in 2005. The Arduino microcontroller was initially designed for professionals and students to create sensor-based communication devices [7]. Arduino microcontrollers' inputs and outputs can be used to obtain information, and Arduino can generate output based on the information it receives. Arduino microcontrollers can transmit and receive data over the internet using HTTP requests [7]. It is possible to separate the hardware and software components of the Arduino platform. Arduino's hardware consists of the development board. The Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment) is the software used to create code by Arduino. These microcontrollers, which have an 8-bit Atmel AVR or a 32-bit Atmel ARM, are easily programmable in C or C++ using the Arduino IDE. When using a USB cable to upload fresh code to an Arduino board, it is feasible to use it for another purpose. Using the Arduino IDE, users may build C or C++ programs for the Arduino platform on almost any personal computer. Utilizing Arduino microcontrollers as compared to other microcontrollers has several advantages. Massimo Banzi, the co-founder of Arduino, provided some compelling arguments for utilizing Arduino boards [10].

Fig 4: Arduino UNO

IV. PROPOSED CIRCUIT

In the proposed circuit, the connections are made from the Arduino UNO board to the RFID Reader.

Fig 5: Arduino – RFID reader connection

The light bulb is connected to the AC power supply and to the relay module. The relay module is then connected to the Arduino UNO board.

Fig 6: Arduino – Relay connection

V. RESULT

After making the connections, the following circuit was created as shown in Fig 7. The following circuit takes 220V input from the AC supply and then connects to the relay module.

Fig 7: Final Build (1)

The RFID reader is able to detect the RFID tag within 7cm. Thus, turning the Light bulb ON, as shown in Fig 8.

Fig 8: Final Build (2)

The light bulb can be turned OFF using the RFID tag in the same way and is shown in Fig 9.

Fig 9: Final Build (3)

Research Through Innovation

VI. CONCLUSION

Touchless operation of the light bulb was achieved by us using an RFID tag and RFID receiver. Further, this project could be scaled even further, by connecting all the appliances in the house using Radio Frequency Identification. Using IoT it could further be scaled using Wi-Fi technology and apps like ThingSpeak.

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